

Online Socialisation and English Language Acquisition among International Students

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Abstract

This study explores the socio-linguistic adaptation by Francophone African students in Nigerian universities, focusing on informal English language acquisition through online socialisation. It examines the dynamics, challenges, and preferences involved in adapting to multi-linguistic environments and aims to offer strategic suggestions for effective informal language learning in such contexts. Quantitative survey type was adopted for the study. A self-administered questionnaire was used in the study to gather primary data from participants who are currently International Students from French-Speaking countries studying in Nigeria Universities using multistage sampling procedure. Four research questions were answered and four hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance using a validated instrument titled Cross-Cultural Language Acquisition Survey (CCLAS; $r=0.92$). Data obtained were analysed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation while inferential statistics of t-test was used to test the hypotheses. The findings showed no gender bias; international students adapted well to informal online language socialisation and acquisition.

It was recommended among others that host universities should implement a multidisciplinary strategy that incorporates language acquisition through online socialisation.

Keywords: Socialisation, digital platforms, language acquisition, cross-cultural, international students

Introduction

Transborder movements in search of education and knowledge frequently occur between countries of the world (KimAnna & Jayoung, 2019). These movements, relating to education, come with challenges that require adaptation to the socio-linguistic, and socio-cultural practices of the host countries by the students (Ma, 2020). The socio-linguistic adaptation occurs both at the formal and informal levels of inter-personal relations through various media. While formal language adaptation requirements for International Students (IS) are often regulated by the host institutions, online socialisation and informal language acquisitions do not require rigid regulations (Beregovaya & Kudashov, 2019).

Focusing on the informal socio-linguistic adaptation of IS provides an understanding of their engagement with different language expressions, styles and idioms (Mcdougald, 2017) . Informal language acquisition by IS improves communication skills enabling them to express themselves confidently in social and academic contexts (Schwieter & Ferreira, 2020). Online socialisation provides an interactive platform for informal language acquisition in digital spaces by IS, thereby promoting an understanding of the socio-linguistic norms of their host country while enhancing a sense of belonging and integration within the Nigerian university system (Schwieter & Ferreira, 2020). Exposure to informal English language acquisition enables IS to become acquainted with colloquial language and informal communication in their environment. This exposure promotes beneficial contributions during lectures, group assignments, and discussions, enhancing academic performance (Granada, 2014; Mendelson, 2010). An understanding of IS informal language acquisition media can enable universities to alleviate formal language acquisition challenges while promoting their psychological well-being, thereby increasing their confidence and self-esteem. An increased proficiency in cross-cultural communication skills prepares IS for diverse professional environments and boosts their contributions to global discourse and collaboration (Indrianti, 2019).

While studies have focused on IS mobility (Yang et al., 2022), associate anxieties relating to second language acquisition, from French to English language (Lin, 2022), the advantages and disadvantages of using technology to acquire language and to teach international students (M. Yang & Shadiey, 2019), research examining language acquisition through online socialisation media among IS, especially in Nigeria, are scarce. There is also a dearth of research that focuses on the unique socio-cultural and linguistics divergence in Nigeria. Also, while there are laid down English language standards to be

met by IS studying in Nigerian university systems, there is inadequate examination of how online socialisation platforms for informal language acquisition contribute either positively or negatively to formal language learning processes among IS. Examining the relationship is necessary for an understanding of language acquisition dynamics in diverse educational settings in the world. The research contributes to knowledge by developing relevant approaches to effective language acquisition strategies and support structures tailored to meet the needs of IS especially in Nigeria and other countries with shared socio-cultural and linguistic characteristics. In addition, the study seeks to contribute to the ongoing discussion on English language acquisition in multicultural environments. It does so by revealing the significance of online socialisation in advancing formal language learning. This revelation assists policy makers in arriving at informed choices in designing L2 acquisition programmes and enhances academic performance of IS in Nigerian universities.

Therefore, the study investigates the dynamics of informal English language acquisition by French speaking students studying in multi socio-linguistics environment prevalent in Nigerian universities. The study identifies the challenges and preferences associated with informal language acquisition for online socialisation. The study consequently provides suggestions on effective informal language acquisition strategies for IS.

Conceptual framework

Understanding Transborder Movements in Education

Transborder movements in education is a multifaceted phenomenon that provides understanding on how students, educators and resources are deployed beyond national boundaries while changing the traditional geopolitical dynamics of education (Uddin, 2022).

This concept encompasses various forms of mobility, including student exchanges, international collaborations between educational institutions, migration of educators seeking employment opportunities abroad, and the global circulation of educational policies and practices (Bernards, 2021; Macklin, 2020; Uddin, 2022).

Understanding transborder movements in education requires a multidisciplinary approach that integrates perspectives from sociology, anthropology, economics, political science, and education studies. Scholars investigate the drivers, dynamics, and implications of these movements, recognising their complex interplay with globalisation, economic development and its drivers such as labour market demands, infrastructural divide, cultural exchange and identity formation, that promote adaptation to

local socio-linguistics dynamics, educational policies, innovation and need for knowledge transfer also contribute to the transborder education dynamics, especially the Bologna Process and UNESCO conventions. The Bologna Process refers to a collective effort among European countries to standardise higher education structures, ensure comparability in qualifications, and promote student and staff mobility across borders. In the context of the passage, the Bologna Process exemplifies how regional educational reforms support transborder education by aligning academic systems, facilitating credit transfers, and enhancing global academic collaboration. It represents a key mechanism for harmonising qualifications and promoting mobility in response to labour market needs and globalisation pressures (Alemu, 2019; Zahavi & Friedman, 2019).

Socio-Linguistic Adaptation

Arrival on campus signifies the beginning of a new journey in socio-linguistic adaptation by all new foreign students. The journey begins with learning vocabulary and grammatical designs (Kamalova et al., 2021) that will ensure a settling down process devoid of socio-linguistic ignorance. The first formal and informal encounters with a new culture and language often necessitate the development of adaptive strategies aimed at addressing the resulting cultural, emotional, linguistic, and social uncertainties (Kamalova et al., 2021). We therefore conceptualise *socio-linguistic adaptation through online socialisation and language acquisition among international students* as a dynamic process shaped by interaction with their new educational environment. This process involves the use of various digital and interpersonal platforms through which non-indigenous learners engage with local linguistic practices. Through these engagements, students gradually internalise the host community's language norms, idioms, and culturally situated modes of communication (Okunade, et al., 2015).

Role of Online Socialisation

Online socialisation remains one of the channels through which international students integrate into the new academic communities due to the capacity to improve interpersonal, peer learning and collaborative skill (Yusof et al., 2022). It provides international students with an opportunity to integrate formally and informally into their new environments while being immersed into the socio-linguistic elements of the new society. The combination of formal and informal features devoid of strict classroom-like regulations afford international students the opportunity to observe, learn and assimilate new socio-linguistic characteristics in a relaxed and informal settings.

Theoretical Framework

This study employs acculturation theory as its theoretical framework to explore the process of acclimatising to a new socio-linguistic environment among international students. John W. Berry (1990, 1997) systematised and theorised acculturation in the context of psychology and intercultural relations (Separa, 2024; Ward, 2008). Acculturation theory posits that the process of adapting to a new cultural context is influenced by one's membership in a social group, which dictates the language, socio-cultural attributes, and characteristics available for assimilation (Cormoş, 2022). Central to this study is the exploration of how acculturation elucidates the manner in which foreign students acquire the socio-linguistic characteristics of their new milieu. Acculturation theory outlines three primary processes by which individuals adapt to the socio-linguistic characteristics of a new environment. The first is assimilation, where individuals adopt the host culture while relinquishing significant aspects of their heritage culture. The second is separation, in which individuals reject the dominant culture and maintain exclusive adherence to their original cultural identity. The third process is integration, which allows individuals to engage with and adopt elements of the new culture while simultaneously preserving key components of their heritage culture (Al-Haddad, 2024). The study, therefore, posits that online socialisation during the acculturation process offers insights into how international students assimilate the cultural and linguistic features of the host culture while either retaining or discarding elements of their heritage cultures (Onayinka et al., 2018). The theoretical framework provides a unique approach; hence, the study seeks perspectives of understanding how French speaking students from francophone West African countries studying in English speaking Anglophone nation like Nigeria. French and English languages are both L2 in the West African countries which bring up other unique expectations such as the challenges of acquiring a new language that is not a language of immediate environment. While previous studies on acculturation have established the challenges associated with it, such as, adjustment patterns contribution to socio-linguistic adaptation of receiving culture (Birman & Simon, 2013), how acculturation may influence more the speaking proficiency rather than pronunciation (Jiang et al., 2009) and the place of foreign students' distance/contact, language deficiency, language power relations in the acculturation process contribute to online socialisation (Park, 2016).

The foregoing challenge may not be captured by the current study. Our focus in this paper therefore is to explore how French speaking foreign students in Nigeria acquire socio-linguistic features of English language through online socialisation. In addition, we seek to understand how such knowledge assists them to meet both their social and academic need as foreign students.

Acculturation theory emphasises that cultural adaptation is a multidimensional, bidirectional process shaped by individual agency, group identity, and sociolinguistic dynamics. It recognises varying adaptation strategies, assimilation, integration, separation based on voluntary or imposed conditions. In multilingual contexts like Nigeria, where English is contextually adapted, international students must navigate linguistic and cultural negotiation. Online socialisation platforms provide informal spaces to manage identity, build communicative competence, and mitigate language-related stress. Thus, the theory offers a critical lens for understanding how French-speaking students acquire socio-linguistic skills and adapt functionally and socially within Anglophone academic environments (Onayinka et al., 2019).

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study is to explore international students' level of Informal Socio-Linguistic Adaptation through online socialisation and language acquisition. The study specifically explore the dynamics of informal English language acquisition among French-speaking students in the multi-socio-linguistic environment prevalent within Nigerian universities; to identify the challenges and preferences associated with informal language acquisition through online socialisation platforms such as WhatsApp, Telegram, Facebook groups, YouTube channels, Instagram live discussions, language exchange apps (e.g., Tandem, HelloTalk), and academic forums among international students from French speaking background and provide recommendations for effective informal language acquisition strategies tailored to the needs of international students, particularly those from Francophone countries, studying in Nigerian universities.

Research Question: As a result of the aim and the objectives stated above, this study answered the following research questions:

What is the level of international students' Informal Socio-Linguistic Adaptation through online socialisation and language acquisition?

1. What are the dynamics of informal English language acquisition among French-speaking students in the multi-socio-linguistic environment prevalent within Nigerian universities?

2. What are the challenges and preferences associated with informal language acquisition through online socialisation platforms among international students from French-speaking backgrounds?
3. What are the perceived recommendations for effective informal language acquisition strategies tailored to the needs of international students, particularly those from French-speaking countries, studying in Nigerian universities?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant gender difference in the level of international students' Informal Socio-Linguistic Adaptation through online socialisation and language acquisition.

H₀₂: There is no significant gender difference in the dynamics of informal English language acquisition among French-speaking students in the multi-socio-linguistic environment prevalent within Nigerian universities.

H₀₃: There is no significant gender difference in the challenges and preferences associated with informal language acquisition through online socialisation platforms among international students from French-speaking backgrounds.

H₀₄: There is no significant gender difference in the perceived recommendations for effective informal language acquisition strategies tailored to the needs of international students, particularly those from French-speaking countries, studying in Nigerian universities.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive quantitative survey research approach. A self-administered questionnaire was used in the study to gather primary data from participants who are currently International Students from French-Speaking countries studying in Nigerian universities.

International Students from French-Speaking countries studying in Nigerian universities made up the study's targeted group. A multistage sampling procedure was employed in the participant selection process. Purposive sampling technique was first used to select the three oldest universities in South west Nigeria who had established foreign students induced socio-linguistic environment for French speaking students, this resulted in the selection of the University of Ibadan, University of Lagos and Obafemi Awolowo University. The targeted group was then identified using the convenience/accidental cum purposive sampling techniques with the conditions of inclusion based on the fact that the participant must be from French speaking countries in Africa, above 18 years of age

and must have spent a minimum of 6 months in the universities, these resulted in the selection of 128 individuals that participated in the study.

Results

The tables below show the analysis of data and results of the study.

Research Question One: What is the level of international students' Informal Socio-Linguistic Adaptation through online socialisation and language acquisition?

Result of the research question was obtained from using descriptive statistical analysis of mean score and standard deviation. The Research question was to find out the level of international students' Informal Socio-Linguistic Adaptation through online socialisation and language acquisition. The grand mean rating of 3.72 with the standard deviation of 0.69 indicated that international students were very much adaptive to Informal Socio-Linguistic processes through online socialisation and language acquisition.

Research Question Two: What are the dynamics of informal English language acquisition among French-speaking students in the multi-socio-linguistic environment prevalent within Nigerian universities?

Result of the research question was obtained from using descriptive statistical analysis of mean score and standard deviation. The Research question was to find out the dynamics of informal English language acquisition among French-speaking students in the multi-socio-linguistic environment prevalent within Nigerian universities. The grand mean rating of 3.44 with the standard deviation of 0.84 indicated favorable dynamics of informal English language acquisition among French-speaking students in the multi-socio-linguistic environment prevalent within Nigerian universities.

Research Question Three: What are the challenges and preferences associated with informal language acquisition through online socialisation platforms among international students from French-speaking backgrounds?

Result of the research question was obtained from using descriptive statistical analysis of mean score and standard deviation. The Research question was to find out the challenges and preferences associated with informal language acquisition through online socialisation platforms among international students from French-speaking backgrounds. The result showed series of challenges and preferences associated with informal language acquisition through online socialisation platforms among international students from French-speaking backgrounds. The grand mean rating of 3.25 with the standard deviation of 0.85

indicated high level of challenges and preferences associated with informal language acquisition through online socialisation platforms among international students from French-speaking backgrounds.

Research Question Four: What are the perceived recommendations for effective informal language acquisition strategies tailored to the needs of international students, particularly those from French-speaking countries, studying in Nigerian universities?

Result of the research question was obtained from using descriptive statistical analysis of mean score and standard deviation. The Research question was to find out the perceived recommendations for effective informal language acquisition strategies tailored to the needs of international students, particularly those from French-speaking countries, studying in Nigerian universities. The grand mean rating of 2.78 with the standard deviation of 0.87 indicated that the prescribed recommendations for effective informal language acquisition strategies tailored to the needs of international students, particularly those from French-speaking countries, studying in Nigerian universities were recommended.

Testing the Hypotheses

Hypotheses were tested using inferential statistics of t-test at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant gender difference in the level of international students’ Informal Socio-Linguistic Adaptation through online socialisation and language acquisition.

Table 6: T-test Analysis of significant gender difference in the level of international students’ Informal Socio-Linguistic Adaptation through online socialisation and language acquisition.

Respondents' Gender	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Err. Mean	df	t	p-value	Decision
Male	75	7.4667	.97722	.11284	1	.488	.722	Not Significant.
Female	53	7.3774	1.07822	.14810	126			Accept H ₀₁

Tables 6 shows $t_{(1,126)} = 0.49$ with p-value of 0.72 computed at an alpha level of 0.05. Since the p-value was greater than the alpha level of 0.05, the null hypothesis was hereby accepted. This shows that there is no significant gender difference in the level of international students’ Informal Socio-Linguistic Adaptation through online socialisation and language acquisition.

H₀₂: There is no significant gender difference in the dynamics of informal English language acquisition among French-speaking students in the multi-socio-linguistic environment prevalent within Nigerian universities.

Table 7: T-test Analysis of significant gender difference in the dynamics of informal English language acquisition among French-speaking students in the multi-socio-linguistic environment prevalent within Nigerian universities.

Respondents' Gender	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Err. Mean	df	t	p- value	Decision
Male	75	31.0533	2.86589	.33092	1	.672	.930	Not Significant. Accept H ₀₂
Female	53	30.7170	2.67738	.36777	126			

Tables 7 shows $t_{(1,126)} = 0.67$ with p-value of 0.93 computed at an alpha level of 0.05. Since the p-value was greater than the alpha level of 0.05, the null hypothesis was hereby accepted. This shows that there is no significant gender difference in the dynamics of informal English language acquisition among French-speaking students in the multi-socio-linguistic environment prevalent within Nigerian universities.

H₀₃: There is no significant gender difference in the challenges and preferences associated with informal language acquisition through online socialisation platforms among international students from French-speaking backgrounds.

Table 8: T-test Analysis of significant gender difference in the challenges and preferences associated with informal language acquisition through online socialisation platforms among international students from French-speaking backgrounds.

Respondents' Gender	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Err. Mean	df	t	p- value	Decision
Male	75	13.3200	1.70183	.19651	1	2.735	.545	Not Significant. Accept H ₀₃
Female	53	12.5094	1.57654	.21655	126			

Tables 8 shows $t_{(1,126)} = 2.74$ with p-value of 0.55 computed at an alpha level of 0.05. Since the p-value was greater than the alpha level of 0.05, the null hypothesis was hereby accepted. This shows that there is no significant gender difference in the challenges and preferences associated with informal language acquisition through online socialisation platforms among international students from French-speaking backgrounds.

H₀₄: There is no significant gender difference in the perceived recommendations for effective informal language acquisition strategies tailored to the needs of international students, particularly those from French-speaking countries, studying in Nigerian universities.

Table 9: T-test Analysis of significant gender difference in the perceived recommendations for effective informal language acquisition strategies tailored to the needs of international students, particularly those from French-speaking countries, studying in Nigerian universities.

Respondents' Gender	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Err. Mean	df	t	p- value	Decision
Male	75	28.0400	2.53324	.29251	1	1.219	.339	Not Significant. Accept H₀₄
Female	53	27.4717	2.68617	.36897	126			

Tables 9 shows $t_{(1,126)} = 1.22$ with p-value of 0.34 computed at an alpha level of 0.05. Since the p-value was greater than the alpha level of 0.05, the null hypothesis was hereby accepted. This shows that there is no significant gender difference in the perceived recommendations for effective informal language acquisition strategies tailored to the needs of international students, particularly those from French-speaking countries, studying in Nigerian universities.

Discussion of Findings

This study has shown that, in addition to having favourable dynamics for informal English language acquisition among French-speaking students in the multi-socio-linguistic environment common in Nigerian universities, international students were very adaptive to informal socio-linguistic processes through online socialisation and language acquisition. This sociolinguistic adaptation happens at both the formal and informal levels of interpersonal relationships through a variety of media. This is in

agreement with the assertion of Mcdougald (2017) who observed that, an understanding of international student's engagement with various language expressions, styles, and idioms can be gained by focusing on the informal sociolinguistic adaptation.

Moreover, the study indicated favorable dynamics of informal English language acquisition among French-speaking students in the multi-socio-linguistic environment prevalent within Nigerian universities. This is in consonance with the claim of Schwieter and Ferreira (2020) that online socialisation offers international students an interactive platform for informal language acquisition in digital spaces, helping them to better understand the sociolinguistic norms of their host country and strengthening their sense of integration and belonging within the Nigerian university system.

As a result, the participants avowed to the prescribed recommendations for efficient informal language acquisition strategies that are specifically designed to meet the needs of international students studying in Nigerian universities. This approves the investigation of how acculturation clarifies how international students pick up the sociolinguistic traits of their new environment where acculturation outlines three main ways in which people integrate the sociolinguistic characteristics of a new environment as assimilation, in which people embrace the new culture while letting go of parts of their old culture; separation, in which people reject the new culture while clinging to their old culture; and integration, which allows people to embrace the receiving culture while preserving the old culture. Furthermore, the investigation found that these results did not significantly differ based on gender.

Conclusion

Since online socialisation can enhance interpersonal, peer learning, and collaborative skills, it continues to be one of the key ways that international students integrate into their new academic communities. It gives international students the chance to immerse themselves in the sociolinguistic components of the new society while assimilating both formally and informally into their new environs. Online socialisation gives international students an interactive platform for informal language learning in digital spaces, which helps them to understand the sociolinguistic norms of their host nation and feel more integrated and at home at the host university. Universities can lessen formal language learning difficulties for overseas students while also supporting their psychological well-being and boosting their self-esteem and confidence by having a better knowledge of their informal language acquisition media. Gaining more experience in cross-cultural communication skills helps foreign students

contribute more to global debate and collaboration and prepares them for a variety of professional settings. International students' transborder movements in online socialisation and language learning are seen as an essential component of how people adapt to changing circumstances brought about by the socioeconomic and educational realities of their day.

Recommendations

The study's findings led to the following recommendations being made:

1. Host universities should implement a multidisciplinary strategy that incorporates language acquisition through online socialisation.
2. Nigeria's university curriculum needs to be modified to take into account the new trends in accepting international students.
3. Academic instructors ought to make efforts to keep up with the rapid advancements in technology.
4. The issues of language barrier, lack of compelling content, cultural variations, and limited access to dependable internet should all be appropriately handled while learning a language informally through online socialisation platforms.

References

- Alemu, S. K. (2019). African higher education and the Bologna Process. *European Journal of Higher Education*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/21568235.2018.1561313>
- Al-Haddad, M. (2024). Facilitating international medical graduates' acculturation: From theory to practice. *Medical Education*, 58(1). <https://doi.org/10.1111/medu.15175>
- Beregovaya, O. A., & Kudashov, V. I. (2019). The problems of linguistic and academic adaptation of international students in Russia. *Integration of Education*, 23(4). <https://doi.org/10.15507/1991-9468.097.023.201904.628-640>
- Bernards, B. (2021). Sinophonic detours in colonial Burma. *Prism*, 18(2). <https://doi.org/10.1215/25783491-9290680>
- Birman, D., & Simon, C. D. (2013). Acculturation research: Challenges, complexities, and possibilities. In *APA handbook of multicultural psychology, Vol. 1: Theory and research*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/14189-011>
- Indrianti, T. (2019). Revisiting the Business English Courses to Meet the Stakeholders' Demand. *Jurnal Linguistik Terapan*, 9(2). <https://doi.org/10.33795/jlt.v9i2.93>

- Jiang, M., Green, R. J., Henley, T. B., & Masten, W. G. (2009). Acculturation in relation to the acquisition of a second language. *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development*, 30(6).
<https://doi.org/10.1080/01434630903147898>
- Kamalova, L. A., Umbetova, M. Z., & Putulyan, N. S. (2021). Technologies and practices of linguistic and sociocultural adaptation of foreign students during their studies at the university. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.30935/cedtech/9312>
- KimAnna, & HAM. JAYOUNG. (2019). Structural characteristics of the global knowledge network reflected in the proliferation of international student mobility. *Korean Journal of Sociology of Education*, 29(2).
<https://doi.org/10.32465/ksocio.2019.29.2.003>
- Lin, Q. (2022). Anxiety and self-efficacy in Chinese international students' L3 French learning with L2 English and L3 French. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.998536>
- Ma, J. (2020). Supporting practices to break chinese international students' language barriers: The first step to facilitate their social adjustment. *Journal of International Students*, 10(1).
<https://doi.org/10.32674/jis.v10i1.773>
- Macklin, A. (2020). (In)Essential Bordering: Canada, COVID, and Mobility. *Frontiers in Human Dynamics*, 2.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fhumd.2020.609694>
- Mcdougald, J. S. (2017). Language and Content in Higher Education TT - Lenguaje y contenido en educación superior Língua e conteúdo no ensino superior. *Latin American Journal of Content & Language Integrated Learning*, 10(1).
- Okunade, J. K., Onayinka, T. S., & Ajijola, A. B. (2015). Mass Communication and Mass Incommunication: A Revisit. *New Media and Mass Communication*, 37, 47–53.
- Onayinka, T. S., A. K. Tsebee, & A. Alao. (2018). Situating Nigeria Newspapers online Readers' Comments within Habermas's Public Sphere. *Babcock Journal of Mass Communication*, 3(1), 125–134.
- Onayinka, T. S., Asogwa, E. C., Ajijola, A. B., & Ige, A. (2019). Influence of Biafra-Related Social Media Contents on the Acceptance of IPOB Agenda in South-East Nigeria. *International Journal of Communication: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Communication Studies*, 24, 50–61.
- Park, E. (2016). International Graduate Students' Second Language Acquisition in Their Acculturation: A Research Synthesis. *English Linguistics Research*, 5(3). <https://doi.org/10.5430/elr.v5n3p21>
- Schwieter, J. W., & Ferreira, A. (2020). Learning a language abroad and the implications for social participation and positioning. *Critical Inquiry in Language Studies*, 17(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/15427587.2020.1713785>
- Separa, L. A. C. (2024). Cultural adaptation experiences of people in New Zealand. *Review of Communication*, 24(2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/15358593.2024.2313238>

- Uddin, N. (2022). The State, Vulnerability, and Uncertainty: The Rohingyas in Myanmar and Bangladesh. In *Voices of the Rohingya People*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-90816-4_4
- Ward, C. (2008). Thinking outside the Berry boxes: New perspectives on identity, acculturation and intercultural relations. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 32(2). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijintrel.2007.11.002>
- Yang, M., & Shadiev, R. (2019). Review of Research on Technologies for Language Learning and Teaching. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 07(03). <https://doi.org/10.4236/jss.2019.73014>
- Yang, Q., Shen, J., & Xu, Y. (2022). Changes in International Student Mobility amid the COVID-19 Pandemic and Response in the China Context. *Fudan Journal of the Humanities and Social Sciences*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40647-021-00333-7>
- Yusof, R., Yin, K. Y., Norwani, N. M., Ahmad, N. L., & Ismail, Z. (2022). Investigating the Role of Digital Learning in Enhancing Educational Values: Online Socialization and Its Effect on Peer Learning, Collaborative Skills and Knowledge Construction. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 21(9). <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.21.9.24>
- Zahavi, H., & Friedman, Y. (2019). The Bologna Process: an international higher education regime. *European Journal of Higher Education*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/21568235.2018.1561314>

